

Co doped SnO₂ nanoparticles for hydrogen gas sensing applications

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The recent advances in the materials science and nanotechnology enabled the development of smart sensors that can detect even very low level concentrations of analyte with high precision. SnO₂ has been extensively used as sensing material for the development and technological implementation of gas sensor and biosensor for various applications. Here, we report that the gas sensing properties of nanostructured SnO₂ could be improved significantly by suitably modifying its properties through various chemical (doping, composite formation, surfactant mediated synthesis) and physical (gamma ray, heavy ion irradiation) approaches.

Hydrogen is a highly flammable gas and will burn at concentrations as low as 4% in. Hence, the hydrogen leak sensors are very much essential for various applications. Resistive sensors based on Mn & Co doped SnO₂ nanoparticles have been fabricated and its sensing performances towards the detection of hydrogen (H₂) were investigated. Results demonstrate that the Co (10 wt%) doping is more effective in enhancing the sensing performance of SnO₂ NPs when compared to pristine and Mn-doped SnO₂, allowing the fabrication of a hydrogen sensor with excellent response and reproducibility at the operating temperature of 250°C. The selectivity of the fabricated sensors against the potential interfering gas carbon monoxide (CO) was also investigated.

Key words: SnO₂ nanoparticles, chemical doping, gamma irradiation, Hydrogen, carbon monoxide.

References:

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